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Submission of comments on the 'New European Innovation Agenda' Initiative

Public Consultation from the European Commission

Comments from:

Name of organisation or individual

Dr Éloïse Gennet, Noémie Dubruel, Prof. Markus Frischhut and Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw and the I-BioLex research project

Please find below the answer to the public consultation on 'the revision of the general pharmaceutical legislation' by **Dr Éloïse Gennet** (*Post-doctoral researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l'Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*), **Noémie Dubruel** (*Juriste en recherche médicale, Doctorante Institut Maurice Hauriou UT1 Capitole et INSERM UMR 1295 BIOETHICS, Toulouse, France*), **Prof. Markus Frischhut** (*Dr., LL.M, Jean Monnet Chair EU Values & DIGitalization for our CommuNITY (DIGNITY), MCI | THE ENTREPRENEURIAL SCHOOL®, Innsbruck, Austria*) and **Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy** (*CNRS Permanent researcher in law, UMR 7318 International, Comparative and European laws-DICE CERIC, Aix Marseille University, Toulon University, Pau & Pays de l'Adour University, Aix-en-Provence, France*), **on behalf of the Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw from the European Association of Health Law (EAHL) and the I-BioLex research project.**

The EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw is co-chaired by Aurélie Mahalatchimy (UMR 7318 DICE CERIC, CNRS, Aix Marseille University, France) and Mark Flear (Queen’s University Belfast, UK) and involved legal experts in Supranational Biolaw, mainly academics, from 14 EU member States, the UK and Switzerland.

The [EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw](#) has been created in 2020 within the European Association of Health Law. It aims to promote European health law, especially in its European-level dimension, regarding the law and the various legal issues arising from technological advances related to medicine and biotechnology. Among its activities, it mobilises its members to address demands from several groups within society, including legislators and regulators, scientists (researchers and clinicians), and patients regarding Supranational Biolaw. The EAHL IG on Supranational Biolaw is also the leader of one of the 2021 Thematic Network of the European Union Health Policy Platform. The Thematic Network is entitled “Health as a fundamental value. Towards an equitable and inclusive pharmaceutical strategy for the EU”. On the basis of webinars and online discussions on the EU Health Policy Platform, it is aimed to produce a Joint Statement to be endorsed as widely as possible. This Joint Statement that will be released in April 2022 on the EU Health Policy Platform will also be particularly relevant in the context of the revision of the pharmaceutical legislation.

Dr Éloïse Gennet, Noémie Dubruel, Prof. Dr Markus Frischhut and Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, are providing this answer on behalf of the EAHL Interest Group on Supranational Biolaw.

The I-BioLex project “**Fragmentation and defragmentation of the law on biomedical innovations**” is funded by the French National Agency for Research (ANR-20-CE26-0007-01, coord. A. Mahalatchimy; 2021-2024). [I-BioLex](#) is exploring whether the processes of fragmentation (division or segmentation), and defragmentation (gathering together, connecting or ‘harmonising’) can jointly contribute to and express the adaptability and coherence of the law as it pertains to Biomedical innovations (BI), in areas such as gene therapy, regenerative medicine, or nanomedicine. Building on the works linked to legal oversight of complex BI, law temporality and law fragmentation phenomenon, I-BioLex uses comparative and interdisciplinary approaches and combines theoretical and empirical elements to test this hypothesis while helping to determine how the law on BI can serve diverse societal objectives.

Dr Éloïse Gennet and Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy are providing this answer on behalf of the I-BioLex Research project.

Dr Éloïse Gennet, Noémie Dubruel, Prof. Markus Frischhut and Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy, are grateful to the European Commission to have been given the opportunity to contribute to this consultation. Please see below our complete answer.

The authors welcome this necessary and timely initiative and acknowledge the crucial importance of the five key issues identified by the Commission in regards to a new European Innovation Agenda: access to finance, pro-innovation regulation, strengthening and connecting of EU innovation ecosystems, better innovation policy making and development of entrepreneurial talent.

In our response, we will tackle these elements with the specific perspective of innovation in the field of health, and more specifically of innovation in the field of pharmaceuticals.

Legal Basis

Article 168 (1) and Article 9 TFEU on “health in all policies” should be added among the legal basis of this initiative.

Although EU competences in health are further delimited by Article 168 TFEU, the commitment to “health in all policies” (Article 168(1) TFEU; Article 9 TFEU) means that the EU has to take into consideration the health impacts of all its activities. Moreover, although the competence for legislative harmonisation of Member State health policies is very restricted, EU powers in health law and policy go far beyond a purely regulatory role. The importance of the EU in taking measures on the administrative and executive levels, including via its agencies, that have effects in all Member States is steadily growing. The EU contributes to knowledge, regulatory capacity and also comparable health data, and steers national health policies through various soft law tools, such as guidance. The EU also executes health policies through the dispersion of funding and through fiscal coordination¹.

In any case, this forthcoming communication, as an Act that is not legally binding but that is an important policy document, should cover innovation in health. Not only does health have to be included in all policies, it (especially e-health and pharmaceuticals) has also been recognised as a “key strategic area” for “creating an innovative Europe”.² In such a context, DG Santé, interacting with other relevant DGs, should be particularly involved in this initiative.

Hence, this initiative which aims to lead to a Communication from the European Commission on a New European Innovation Agenda should also necessarily be based on Articles 168(1) and 9 TFEU.

Respect of fundamental rights

Even when innovation is intended to bring improvements to society, it may also bring with itself unintended - including unexpected - risks to the protection of individual and collective human rights. Careful attention should be drawn to providing appropriate safeguards to fundamental rights when developing a governance framework for innovation.

¹ SL Greer, “The Three Faces of European Union Health Policy: Policy, Markets, and Austerity” (2014) 33(1) *Policy and Society* 13–24.

² Report of the Independent Expert Group on R&D and innovation appointed following the Hampton Court Summit and chaired by Mr. Esko Aho, Creating an Innovative Europe, 20 January 2006, EUR22005, p.8: <http://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/aho_report.pdf>.

The future Commission communication on a New European Innovation Agenda should recall the importance of respecting fundamental rights and most importantly the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU.

The future communication should also recall the importance of the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade³, especially given the strong link between this initiative and the digital transition.

Societal aspects of European innovation

We would like to stress the importance, when considering the need to increase innovation cohesion, to not only take into account economic and technological aspects of innovation but rather also take into account its **societal aspects**. The benefits of innovation should be directed to all, both individually and collectively, which entails the necessity to take positive action to direct innovation towards vulnerable groups and unmet health needs.

The necessity to align innovation with societal needs is reflected in many EU policy instruments and initiatives. According to the Expert Group on the State of the Art in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation⁴, “**Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** refers to the comprehensive approach of proceeding in research and innovation in ways that allow all stakeholders that are involved in the processes of research and innovation at an early stage (A) to obtain relevant knowledge on the consequences of the outcomes of their actions and on the range of options open to them and (B) to effectively evaluate both outcomes and options in terms of societal needs and moral values and (C) to use these considerations (under A and B) as functional requirements for design and development of new research, products and services” (p. 3). We thus encourage the Commission to take this report into account when elaborating the Communication to establish the RRI approach “as a collective, inclusive and system-wide approach” and thus “better coordinate” efforts, “avoid failed investments” and “better exploit the potential of considering societal needs in innovation” (p. 3).

Health Innovation

- *Health Innovation as a strategic policy field to be acknowledged in the New European Innovation Agenda*

It can be considered that it exists an implicit European innovation strategy in health as long as health innovation is transversal and currently integrated within other Union strategies: the Union economic strategy (especially from the Lisbon Strategy), the Research & Innovation strategy (Innovation Union, EU Framework programmes for Research & Innovation, European

³ European Commission, European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade, COM(2022) 28 final, Brussels, 26 January 2022.

⁴ Expert Group on the State of the Art in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation, Options for Strengthening, Responsible Research and Innovation, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation Science in Society, 2013.

Research area with European research infrastructures adopted on the legal basis of article 187 TFEU), Life science and biotechnology strategy⁵, and public health strategy⁶.

What was stated in the 2002 life science and biotechnology strategy is still true for innovation in health: “Europe does not have a single policy for [innovation in health] but a patchwork of specific regulation, overlaid by many sectoral and horizontal policies at international, Community, Member State and local levels. If, with so many actors and policies involved, Europe is to successfully manage [innovation in health] and reap the benefits for society, we should proceed on the basis of a shared vision for a co-operative approach and with effective implementing mechanisms to compensate for absence of overall responsibility and control. Without such mechanisms, [innovation in health] risk to continue to suffer indecision or short-sighted and local solutions.”⁷

Recognizing the existence of a European innovation strategy in health would make it possible to optimize the use of the range of competences of the European Union, while respecting national competences, in the fields associated with health innovation: economics, research & innovation and public health.⁸ It would make clear the interest of a transversal European action already at work in order to rebalance the European objectives considered and to ensure an overall coherence to concrete and scattered legal activities. Hence, it would also be easier to assess the extent of past, current and future European action in the field and of its specificity by making it more understandable to European citizens and involving them.

The resulting overall action would be more transparent. It would provide reliable benchmarks to players in the field while guaranteeing the necessary flexibility to take into account the evolution of science and technology in the field of health innovation.

Finally, the identification and clarification of the values and legal principles underlying this strategy would allow the European Union to look to the future by basing its uniqueness on its values⁹, including the reaffirmation of health as a fundamental value as it has been accepted by the EU Council since at least 2006, and arguably much longer.¹⁰

- *Human rights to be acknowledged regarding technologies and innovation in biomedicine and health*

⁵ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Life sciences and biotechnology — A strategy for Europe, COM(2002) 27, JO C 55 du 2 mars 2002, pp. 3–32.

⁶ Notably and lastly based on Regulation (EU) 2021/522 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 March 2021 establishing a Programme for the Union’s action in the field of health (‘EU4Health Programme’) for the period 2021-2027, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 282/2014, OJ L 107, 26.3.2021, p. 1–29.

⁷ COM(2002) 27, op. cit. p. 19-20.

⁸ For further discussion on why and how a European innovation strategy in health should be reaffirmed at the Union policy level, please see: A. Mahalatchimy, Pour une stratégie de l’Union européenne dans le domaine de l’innovation en santé, Revue de l’Union Européenne, Janvier 2019, n°624, pp. 22-29.

⁹ Translated from French « regarder vers l’avenir en fondant sa singularité sur des valeurs », J. L. QUERMONNE, L’Union européenne dans le temps long, Presses de Sciences Po, Paris, 2008, p. 20.

¹⁰ Article 2 of the original European Economic Community (EEC) Treaty stated that one of the objectives of the EEC was “raising of the standard of living”, at least arguably for everyone present in the EEC, which would point to health protection and promotion as an EU value even from those earliest days, see TK Hervey and JV McHale, *Health Law and the European Union* (Cambridge University Press, 2004), pp 72-73.

This initiative should also take into account the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine.

Moreover, we want to draw the attention of the Commission on the activities of the Council of Europe in regards to technologies and innovation in biomedicine and health. In fact, in its Strategic Action Plan¹¹, the Steering Committee for Human Rights in the fields of Biomedicine and Health (CDBIO) (formerly the Committee on Bioethics or DH-BIO) is planning, among others, to target two issues of particular interest regarding innovation.

- First, it is planning to target governance models of technologies in order to embed human rights in the development of technologies as the full extent of (unintended) consequences of innovation can often only be evaluated when innovation, such as digital innovation, has already been adopted in society.
 - Second, it is planning to promote equity in healthcare and therefore to elaborate a draft recommendation on “equitable and timely access to innovative treatments and technologies in healthcare”.
- *Establishing a specific EU entity within DG-SANTE to support gene and cell therapy development*

This entity, that could be similar to the Gene and Cell Therapy Catapult in the UK, would foster gene and cell therapy development in the European Union, relying on the exceptional regulatory anticipation that has occurred in the field of Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products in the European Union. It would particularly target the key bottleneck identified in this initiative for this area of health innovation. For instance, it could provide support for establishing public-private partnerships, take stock of fiscal measures that could attract capital risk investments, identify key areas for training in needed skills and recruitment of EU and non-EU talent, contribute to the framing for the collection of real-world evidence through interoperable (European) registries in the European Union in order to ensure the quality and robustness of long-term safety and efficacy data (in relation to the European Health Data Space) to support European bioproduction, marketing authorisation, and to support full Health technology Assessment, provide support for innovative payment models to be established in the European Member States¹², provide support to strengthen and connect innovation ecosystems through the whole lifecycle of a medicinal product, from funding of fundamental research and clinical trials through joint procurement¹³ of biomedical innovations, etc...

¹¹ <https://rm.coe.int/strategic-action-plan-final-e/1680a2c5d2>

¹² To this end, the Expert Panel on Effective Ways of Investing in Health (EXPH) 2018 opinion on “Innovative payment models for high-cost innovative medicines” (https://ec.europa.eu/health/system/files/2019-11/opinion_innovative_medicines_en_0.pdf) should be taken into account.

¹³ Public procurement is seen in the Commission’s Pharmaceutical Strategy as a policy area that could foster competition and improve access (Pharmaceutical Strategy, p. 7). The European Parliament, in its resolution of 16 February on strengthening Europe in the fight against cancer, strongly advocates in favor of the extension of joint procurement procedures, notably but not only for rare and paediatric cancer or diseases, as such procedures should improve timely and affordable access for patients.

- *Disruptive innovation in the field of health*

Specific attention should be given to disruptive innovation in the field of health, taking into account the Expert Panel on Effective Ways of Investing in Health (EXPH) 2016 opinion entitled “Disruptive Innovation. Considerations for health and healthcare in Europe”¹⁴, especially its following aspects:

- This opinion distinguishes between non-disruptive innovations - which “do not create new markets or value network but rather better value by continuous improvement within an established system for reward of innovation for the different stakeholder” (p. 7) - and disruptive innovations - which “create new networks and organizational changes (based on a new set of values) and involve new players, leading to improvements in value as well as changes in the distribution of value between different stakeholders. In fact, disruptive innovations displace older organisational structures, workforce, processes, products, services and technologies” (p. 7).
- Interestingly, the EXPH insists on patient-centered innovations: it defines the promotion of person-centered health delivery or the empowerment of patient and persons as one possible characteristic of a disruptive innovation (p. 7); it stresses the importance of patient engagement in the promotion and development of disruptive innovations - as well as all relevant actors (p. 8).
- The EXPH explains the notion of “disruptive innovations” as initially conceptualized by Christensen (1997)¹⁵ in order to apply it to the European health care context. The idea is that “disruptive innovations” simplify services or technologies and make them more affordable and thus more accessible, which is particularly relevant for instance regarding patient-centered health delivery, therapy and care (pp. 13-14) (...) “European Health Systems are based on the values of universality, equity, solidarity and access to high quality and safety services. The respect of these values is a precondition when talking of innovation. (...) A disruptive innovation would be one that allows generalized access to a product or a service previously accessible only to the ones with a higher need or the ones not facing high barriers to access” (p. 22).
- “Disruptive innovations are not necessarily “advanced technologies”. Disruptive innovations are often novel combinations of existing off-the-shelf components, applied cleverly to a small, fledgling value network. Many disruptive innovations result from the combination of one or more innovative technologies and their application through innovative business models” (p. 20).

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/health/publications/disruptive-innovation-health-care-considerations-future_en

¹⁵ Christensen CM (1997). *The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail*. Harvard Business Press.